

ADHESION EVALUATION IN CARBON FIBER/CONCRETE MATRIX COMPOSITES

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1 General Introduction

Over one hundred and fifty years of knowledge and use of Portland cement, steel bars have been applied as concrete reinforcement, both in manufacturing a simple well cover and in building large works such as tunnels, bridges and dams. However, from the mid last century, the use of non-metallic fibers associated with mortar, bricks and floors began to be effectively studied to obtain composites that would offer advantages to steel rebar structures. From such knowledge, propositions arose for using different types of fibers to reinforce structural elements [1] such as beams and pillars of highways and bridges that had undergone some kind of damage by excessive overload or even for some structural adequacy in commercial buildings by changing the type of use [2], for recovering architectural features or restoring historic buildings [3]. The expansion of that knowledge suggests experimenting its application in civil construction regarding the recovery of structures which suffer continuous action of aggressive agents, like acid rain for example, and/or when they are submitted to a load that is beyond the strength limit they have been designed for, which might be a consequence of the alterations on their initially proposed characteristics [4]. However, studies on structures of cement matrix composites with continuous synthetic fiber have been barely related in the literature [5]. Still, there has been an increasing number of studies on applications of macro fibers, fabric or mats to compensate axial, flexural and shear requirements. Here are some examples of those applications: Adia Building (Dubai, United Arab Emirates), Parking Garage (Lucerna, Switzerland) and Wadhwa Building (Mumbai, India). In Brazil, that technique was applied in the reinforcements made in Marriot Hotel and in Globo Network TV Tower, both in Rio de Janeiro [6]. The macro fibers are used to improve the concrete toughness in floors and to decrease the thickness for the projected concrete. In order to replace the traditional metallic structures by continuous carbon fibers reinforcement elements in

concrete elements industrially produced, the researchers will have to make a huge research effort, among other factors, due to the lack of techniques and also to the high cost of those fibers. The aim of the present work was to obtain bond strength values through pullout tests and evaluate the properties of fiber/cement interface. The obtained values were compared to the results of pullout tests done in concrete specimens with corrugated steel bars, which are daily used in civil construction. In the present work, the adhesion of fiber/cement interface was evaluated by manufacturing concrete specimens with compression resistance (f_{ck}) of 29 Nmm² at 28 days. A continuous carbon fiber rod, 250 mm long, was prepared and inserted 50 mm length in the concrete block. Several specimens were submitted to pullout tests and the bond strength values were compared to the results for concrete specimens with steel bars, which are daily used in civil construction, also obtained in pullout tests. In the present work, evaluations will be made according to civil engineering regulations and constructive procedures and, in lack of those, procedures and testing suitable to the purpose of the present study will be proposed.

2. Concepts of matrix

The term composite means the combination of at least two different materials in macroscopic scale, with their phases separated by a distinct interface, making a unit whose properties neither of the components shows individually. Therefore, in a project that uses that material, it is possible to define the mechanic characteristics that are desired to meet certain applications. It is different from metallic alloys whose combinations occur in atomic scale. In other words, the composites basic characteristic is to combine appropriately at least two distinct phases, named matrix and reinforcement, in order to meet the requirements of a project [5]. In a composite material the fibrous materials may be natural or artificial. Among the existing natural materials, the vegetal fibers present cellulosic nature, easy to be

prepared and inexpensive. However, its durability can be compromised by the alkaline character of cement matrices and by the variations in the fiber diameter in the presence of humidity, which may be partially solved with previous waterproofing treatment of the material. Those fibers are abundantly available in nature as well as when they are byproducts of industrialized materials; they show great applicability when they are incorporated to cement matrices or to raw land [7]. The asbestos fibers, regarded as natural fibers, have their use very restricted because its manipulation during all manufacturing cycle was considered harmful to health. Equally qualified as natural mineral, fiber glass, produced from stretching by gravity and further cooling of an incandescent mass with varied percentages of silica, potassium, alumina, sodium, magnesium, calcium and cleaned glass leftovers results in an inorganic, homogeneous and amorphous substance. Although type E glass fiber is used to manufacture many polymeric composite components, providing excellent performance in neutral environments; to withstand alkaline environments, such as concrete, for instance, it is necessary to use glass fiber alkali resistant (AR).

The third subdivision of natural materials regards animal fibers, which are not used in the manufacturing of cement composites.

In the literature, the use of discontinuous fibers in civil construction is recommended to control deformations and cracks as well as to be added to concrete in order to improve the resistance to strain. The phase called matrix of a composite material is continuous and involves reinforcement. In case of a cement matrix composite, it is composed by cement, small aggregate (sand), large aggregate (gravel) and water. During the manufacturing of an element of concrete, the cement hardening occurs by the addition of water in pre defined proportions and by an exothermic chemical reaction which, if not properly treated, may provoke cooling of the outer layers and cause retraction while the nucleus remains warm and dilated [8]. After the concrete curing, the result will be a hard and homogeneous structure in which the bond strength between the parts will be due to the physical friction between its components, and the structure stability will be kept by the actions absorption by the matrix as well as by the reinforcement material. The bond strength guarantees the bonding of the armed concrete components whose hardening results in a frictional

strength (a physical action) between the mixture components, which is given by the existing roughness in steel bars as well as by the folds in the breakpoints of traction elements [8].

3. Concepts of interface

3.1 Fiber/ cement matrix

The interface fiber/matrix is an important link between the composite structure materials because it takes the matrix loading strain to the reinforcement (fibers). It can be defined as the area close to the fibers surface and next to the matrix that involves them. Regarding the meaningful difference in the elastic properties of the composite raw materials, it is the interface that will harmonize them. As an example, it is important to point out that the modulus of elasticity of a cement matrix is 30 GPa, while the carbon fiber of high mechanical resistance is 230 GPa. Knowing the interface properties, which are specific for each fiber/matrix system, is fundamental to understand the physical and mechanical properties of composite materials and extremely important concerning the resistance to material fracture. The results obtained in this analysis are important to evaluate the mechanical behavior of the laminate. The resistance of the coupling fiber to matrix is ensured by mechanical action, and in polymeric composites there is still the resistance due to the resulting action of presence of functional groups on the fiber surface, as on the carbon fiber, for example, where they are inserted by some electrolytic treatment in the final stage of manufacturing and whose goal is to create affinity with the polymeric matrix and provide better bonding. However, the cement matrix cannot perform an efficient chemical bond to the carbon fiber. So, a superficial finishing on the fiber surface was made to allow an efficient mechanical bond between these two materials. It consisted of inserting elements that increased the material roughness in the fiber surface, as shown in Fig.1.

Fig. 1. Interface fiber/cement matrix.

A test used to determine the resistance of interface fiber/matrix is the one that uses the assembling represented in Fig. 2 [9]. In this case, the specimen is formed by a polymeric matrix disk with a rod in its center.

Fig. 2. Pullout test to determine the shearing resistance of interface fiber/matrix.

The test is simple and the matrix disk is held by an appropriate device and the fiber is conveniently tractioned. The shearing resistance is determined by the expression (1)

$$\tau_i = \frac{F}{\pi dt} \quad (1)$$

where F is the strength to break the link fiber/matrix, d is the rod diameter and t is the fiber length stuck to concrete.

Considering the shearing and traction strengths which act on the length element dx , Fig. 3, indicated respectively by equations (2) and (3) and their balance by equation (4), there is the shear tension along the interface by equation (5).

Fig. 3. Balance of strengths in a dx length reinforcement element on the interface fiber/matrix.

$$\frac{dP}{dx} dx = (2\pi r_f \cdot dx) \tau_i \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dP}{dx} = \pi r_f^2 \frac{d\sigma_f}{dx} \quad (3)$$

$$(\pi r_f^2 \frac{d\sigma_f}{dx}) \cdot dx = 2\pi r_f \cdot dx \cdot \tau_i \quad (4)$$

or yet

$$\tau_i(x) = \frac{r_f}{2} \frac{d\sigma_f}{dx} \quad (5)$$

The method used to determine the friction resistance was the pullout test, which consists of measuring the necessary traction strength to break the link between the composite phases and move the reinforcement out of the cement matrix. Once the link fiber/cement matrix is broken, the test is interrupted and the pullout strength in that moment is considered the strength limit for that sample. The shear or bond tension may then be obtained by the relation between the traction strength at the moment of sliding and the initial area of the fiber anchoring in the concrete block.

3.2 Steel bar/cement matrix

Most of construction steel is produced with grooves which cause friction on the interface steel/cement matrix, as shown in Fig. 4. This geometric characteristic prevents the sliding between the two phases of the matrix up to the concrete or the groove

resistance limit. As long as this condition is met, the structure will remain stable. In order to keep the fiber stuck to the matrix and determine the resistance in the interface fiber/cement matrix, it is necessary to evaluate the bond resistance (friction) between the two phases of the composite.

Fig. 4. Representation of the friction zone generated by the grooves in a steel bar submitted to traction strains.

4 Materials and Testing Methods

4.1 Concrete matrix

The concrete matrix itself is a three-phase composite which consists of cement, small and large aggregates. Its physical characteristics are directly related to the percentages of each mixture component and the necessary water volume, chosen in accordance to the last resistance and geometry of the calculated parts for this work. In the present study, the concrete presented compression characteristic resistance (f_{ck}) of 29 Nmm^{-2} , obtained from the water-cement ratio of 0.53, by using cement proportions type CP 32, medium washed sand and n°1 gravel of respectively 1: 2.24 : 2.34, as illustrated in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. A specimen of concrete matrix composites.

Conceptually, a composite material allows the engineer to quantify the percentages of each mixture component in order to create a new material for every application need considering the applied load and its effects. In other words, the calculus engineer can highlight some desirable characteristics and minimize other undesirable ones through a calculated combination of components [10]. In Tab.1 the amounts of each cement matrix component related to a 50 Kg cement bag are indicated to mold the specimens in the mentioned proportions.

Tab.1 Concrete proportions for specimens molding with $f_{ck} = 29 \text{ Nmm}^{-2}$

Description	Amount (Kg)
Cement	50.00
Medium washed sand	112.00
Gravel n° 1	117.00
Water	26.50

4.2 Polymeric Matrix

The mixture in suitable proportions of resin, hardener and accelerator makes a solid material named polymeric matrix, which has good mechanic properties and great chemical resistance when conveniently cured. The term resin, as it is often used, can refer either to resin or to polymeric matrix, so attention must be paid regarding its interpretation [8]. The polymeric matrix used to mold the rod was obtained from the mixture of materials MY750 (resin), HY2918 (hardener) and DY062 (accelerator), prepared, in the case of the present work, for heat curing.

4.3 Carbon fiber

Carbon fibers result from a treatment in preliminary organic fibers, or derived from oil or coal in inert environment, from fiber oxidation and thermal procedure at high temperatures. That results in some material with carbon atoms perfectly aligned along the fiber, which provides excellent mechanical resistance to the final product. Some other characteristics of that material are good behavior to fatigue and to action of cyclic loads, chemical resistance to high corrosion, thermal stability and rheology, and it is extremely light [10]. In order to better understand the method, rod is the name given to a fiber length that received a superficial treatment to increase fiber/cement bond and it will react to strengths (internal forces, action effects) due to loads in the concrete structure [8]. Rods are a composite material that combines the carbon fiber, which does not suffer plastic deformation, and a polymeric matrix, which keeps the fibers bonded in parallel. The basic characteristics of composite materials are combining the characteristics of at least two materials in order to obtain a material that offers better performance than those two separately; in other words, the composite consists of a multiphase material, artificially made, composed of chemically different phases and separated by a distinct interface [6]. Continuous carbon-fiber rod, 250 mm length, was prepared and inserted 50 mm length in the concrete block. The several specimens were submitted to pullout tests and the bond strength values were compared to the results obtained in concrete steel bars specimens, which are daily used in civil construction, also obtained in pullout tests. In the present work, a Toray T700 carbon fiber with 12,000 filaments (12K), filament diameter of 7 μm and roving section 0.46 mm^2 , which does not suffer plastic deformation, was used. The strength, modulus and density of the carbon fiber used in the present study are shown in Tab. 2.

Tab. 2. Properties of the carbon fiber Toray T700.

Properties	Value
Tensile strength (Nmm^{-2})	4,900
Tensile modulus (GPa)	230
Density (g.cm^{-3})	1.8

4.4 Steel bar

In a piece of armed concrete, the steel bars are placed within the formworks before the polymeric concrete is cast, involving them. After hardening a piece of armed concrete is obtained.

The bond between those two materials is responsible for transferring the shear, torsion and bending strains from the concrete to the steel bars [8]. Those bars, due to the concrete porosity, are exposed to the attack of chemical substances and weathering, which may lead to the collapse of the armed concrete pieces due to the swelling and rupture of the protective concrete layer. In the present work, as a comparative element between the reinforcement material proposed as a rod, a steel bar segment traditionally used in concrete structures in civil construction, 25 cm long and 6.4 mm diameter was equally tested. The test determined value with the steel element will be the reference.

4.5 Specimens manufacturing

In order to avoid any fiber twist during the pullout test, the specimens were manufactured by choosing a two blocks arrangement, as shown in Fig. 6. Each concrete block has the dimension of 100 x 100 x 100 mm, and a plastic hose was placed through a hole in the formwork side to isolate the fiber in 50 mm from the concrete as shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 6. Carbon-Fiber-cement composites specimens to pullout tests.

Fig. 7. Detail of formwork with isolating tube.

Next, the formworks were filled with concrete in 25 mm layers and manually compacted. The samples were left outdoors for 3 hours and after that they were immersed in alkali saturated water (ph 12) for a 28-day period, as shown in Fig. 8.

The samples were kept outdoors for about 3 hours until the beginning of the cement matrix curing process and then they were immersed in a tank of pH alkaline water where they remained for 28 days. The formworks were removed after the first 24 hours of curing, Fig. 9.

Fig. 8. Double formwork to fuse specimens, highlighting the plastic tube for isolation.

Fig. 9. Samples underwater curing por 28 days.

4.6 Pullout tests

To evaluate the physical behavior of the interface among carbon fiber filaments and a concrete matrix of known resistance, several concrete samples were prepared and submitted to the pullout test. Fig. 10 shows a schematic arrangement of the pullout test.

Fig. 10. Sample dimensions for the pullout test.

To make the sample with steel bar reinforcement, a formwork was prepared with only one concrete block since the testing universal machine grip fits perfectly the tip of the steel bar. The pullout tests were developed in an Instron testing universal machine model 4400R. The test speed was $0.5 \text{ mm} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$. Fig. 11 shows the steel bar and the isolating tube in the formwork. Fig. 12 shows the single block test in progress.

Fig. 11. 6.4 mm diameter steel bar chosen as reinforcement.

Fig. 12 Single-block test device technique.

For double blocks arrangement, each concrete block was placed in a separate metal support to measure the fiber pullout strength, as shown in Fig. 13.

Fig. 13. Two-block test device technique apparatus assembled for testing.

5 Results

Concerning the two concrete blocks assembly, the loading up to the rupture point reached the average level of 10,890 N. The pullout test of a corrugated steel bar in the single concrete block testing method resulted in the average value of 8,000 N. A relevant aspect was observed regarding the carbon fiber rods testing: in the double blocks testing, the rods of some specimens ruptured out of the concrete block before there was a slide (friction loss) in the interface fiber/concrete.

6 Conclusions

Preliminary results showed that composite concrete specimens with carbon fiber had a bond strength average value of 10.67 Nmm², whereas in the concrete specimens manufactured with steel bars the bond strength average value was 7.96 Nmm², considering the reinforcement and steel bar diameters of respectively 6.5 and 6.4 mm. Based on these results, it is possible to identify a significant increase of 34% in fiber/cement bond strength value by using carbon fiber when compared to steel bars

and cement matrix composites, both with concrete matrix of 29 Nmm² compression resistance at 28 days. However, it is necessary to improve the test assembly system in order to avoid the rods rupture during loading process. Thus, it will be possible to measure the real friction strength value in the interface fiber/concrete matrix.

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